

ANTIARRHYTHMIC THERAPY FOR ATRIAL FIBRILLATION IN ELDERLY PATIENTS

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Abstract. Atrial fibrillation is one of the most common and clinically significant cardiac arrhythmias. Most patients with atrial fibrillation requiring treatment are elderly and senile persons with comorbid pathology. The review article presents data on the choice of strategy and tactics for managing such patients, the selection of antiarrhythmic drug therapy aimed at restoring and maintaining sinus rhythm or at slowing down the ventricular rhythm. The possibilities of using atrial radiofrequency ablation and subsequent administration of antiarrhythmic drugs are considered, taking into account the existing international recommendations.

Key words: atrial fibrillation, cardiac insufficiency, dyspnoe.

Relevance. Atrial fibrillation (AF) is the most common cardiac arrhythmia in clinical practice, and is increasingly common due to an aging population. [1,3] The prevalence of atrial fibrillation is 6% in elderly and senile people and about 2% in the entire population. In 6-10% of patients with coronary artery disease, the disease is complicated by atrial fibrillation, and in patients with mitral heart disease requiring surgical treatment, atrial fibrillation develops in 60-80% of cases. Observations indicate a significant increase in the incidence of this arrhythmia. AF is associated with an increase in mortality (general, cardiovascular, sudden), the risk of stroke and systemic thromboembolism, heart failure, acute coronary syndromes, and a deterioration in the quality of life. Recent years have seen significant advances in the treatment of patients with AF. [2,4,5]

The prevalence of atrial fibrillation (AF) increases with age, which is the most common arrhythmia in patients over 65 years of age. The prevalence of AF is increasing in parallel with the aging of the population. AF itself cannot be considered directly lifethreatening, but it is undoubtedly associated with an increased risk of death. In the Framingham cohort, the overall mortality rate was 1.5 for men and 1.9 for women with AF, even after adjusting for age and other risk factors. In addition, morbidity in elderly patients with AF is of great importance because these patients have increased risk of heart failure, stroke, need for pacemaker implantation, and side effects associated with antiarrhythmic therapy. pincha is hospitalized for a long time. Although this arrhythmia has been recognized since the ancient civilizations of China, Egypt and Greece, its treatment and management remains a challenge for modern physicians. Recent advances in drug therapy and invasive methods have opened new horizons in the field of AF. Elderly patients who were previously excluded from trials are now actively involved in various studies, thereby offering new solutions to medical science to manage and treat this age group. This review highlights the management of AF in very elderly patients.

Objectives. Evaluation of the results of treatment by various methods of elderly patients with atrial fibrillation.

Material and methods. The study included patients with transient AF who were inpatient treatment. Most of the patients received AARP, i.e. the so-called hybrid therapy, beta-blockers, in addition to them, drugs of III and IC classes were used. These groups were comparable in age (mean age 64.9 and 64.7 years, respectively), gender, and underlying pathology.

Conclusion: In elderly patients with recurrent atrial fibrillation, hybrid therapy is more effective for maintaining sinus rhythm compared to drug therapy, and drug AAT is safer for maintaining sinus rhythm. Age should not be a reason for refusing to undergo surgery. When choosing the tactics of rational AAT in elderly patients, preference should be given to tactics in which it is possible to achieve an improvement in the quality of life.

References:

1. McLaughlin W., Oudiz R. J., Frost A. et. al. Randomized study of adding inhaled iloprost to existing bosentan in pulmonary arterial hypertension // *Am. J. Respir. Crit. Care Med.* - 2006. - Vol. 174. - P. 1257-63.
2. Lang I., Gomes-Sanches M., Kneussi M. et. al. Efficacy of longterm subcutaneous treprostinil sodium in pulmonary hypertension // *Chest.* - 2006. - Vol. 129. - P. 1636-43.
3. Galie N., Humbert M., Vachiery J.L. et. al. Effect of beraprost sodium, an oral prostacyclin analogue, in pulmonary arterial hypertension: a randomized, double-blind placebo-controlled trial // *JACC.* - 2002. - Vol. 39. -- P. 1496-502.
4. Rubin L. J., Mendoza J., Hood M. et. al. Treatment of primary pulmonary hypertension with continuous intravenous prostacyclin (epoprostenol). Results of a randomized trial // *Ann. Intern. Med.* - 1990. - Vol. 11. - P. 485-91.
5. Galie N., Rubin U., Jansa P. et. al. Treatment of patients with mildly symptomatic pulmonary arterial hypertension with bosentan (EARLY study): a doubleblind, randomized, controlled trial // *Lancet.* - 2008. - Vol. 371. - P. 2093-2100.